

Aerobic Photobleaching of Riboflavin - Involvement of the Singlet State

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The photochemical bleaching of riboflavin and riboflavin 5'-phosphate (also known as flavin mononucleotide) under different conditions has been studied by various authors¹⁻⁴. Under anaerobic conditions by using various inhibitors of the photobleaching reaction it has been found that their inhibitory effects were much greater on the photobleaching reaction than their ability to quench the fluorescence of riboflavin. This has led to the conclusion

that the anaerobic photobleaching of riboflavin predominantly involves the photoexcited triplet state. However, in natural surroundings, irradiation and hence photobleaching of riboflavin occurs under aerobic condition. It is therefore important that the mechanism of aerobic photobleaching of riboflavin be studied in detail. Song and Metzler¹ reported the kinetics of photobleaching of riboflavin in ethanol and suggested that the excited singlet state

of riboflavin is primarily responsible for photobleaching and lumichrome formed by intramolecular photodealkylation of riboflavin was found to be the major product^{1,4}. In presence of 3-indole-acetic acid the photobleaching of riboflavin was found to originate from the singlet state, both in anaerobic and aerobic conditions⁵. Also, Gladys and Knappe⁶ measured the quantum yields for intramolecular photodealkylation of riboflavin and have suggested that this reaction proceeds via the first excited singlet state in aerobic condition. It can, therefore, be concluded from these studies that in presence of oxygen, which is a very efficient quencher of flavin triplet state, the photobleaching reaction should proceed mostly through the singlet state of riboflavin. However, no experimental study seems to have been undertaken to establish this hypotheses. In this paper we have studied the kinetics of aerobic photobleaching of riboflavin in aqueous solution in presence of two inhibitors, KI and KBr and have made a comparison of the results so obtained with Stern-Volmer quenching constants of riboflavin fluorescence by the same quenchers. The results of our study fit in remarkably well with a scheme where aerobic photobleaching of riboflavin initiates from its photoexcited singlet state.

Results and Discussion

In connection with the photobleaching of riboflavin under aerobic condition the following scheme may be considered^{1,7}:

where Rf is riboflavin molecule, Q and Q' are the quenchers, Rf₀ is the ground, ¹Rf the excited singlet and ³Rf is the triplet state of riboflavin. Riboflavin is excited to its singlet state ¹Rf upon absorption of light (step 1). It may then go back to the ground state, giving up the energy as fluorescence (step 2), may be quenched by a quencher (step 3) or may go to the triplet ³Rf by intersystem crossing (ISC) (step 4). This ³Rf may also undergo quenching (step 5). The photobleaching reaction product, lumichrome, is formed from ¹Rf through an intramolecular cyclisation reaction¹ (step 6).

In presence of oxygen (step 5, Q' = O₂), which is an efficient quencher of flavin triplet state ($k_5 = 1.7 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)⁸ but has little effect on the singlet state⁷, the steady state concentration of ³Rf is very small and if we neglect the same the quantum yield of photobleaching, ϕ is given by

$$\phi = \frac{I_{\text{abs}} k_6}{k_2 + k_3[\text{Q}] + k_4 + k_6} \quad (1)$$

where k 's are the rate constants. Quantum yield ϕ_0 in absence of quencher Q becomes

$$\phi_0 = \frac{I_{\text{abs}} k_6}{k_2 + k_4 + k_6} \quad (2)$$

Since the rate of photobleaching is much slower than the rates of the photophysical processes, we assume the establishment of a photostationary state and hence the quantum yield of photobleaching is proportional to the overall photobleaching rate constant, k , from equations (1) and (2) we obtain

$$\frac{\phi_0}{\phi} = \frac{k_0}{k} = 1 + \frac{k_3[\text{Q}]}{k_2 + k_4 + k_6} \quad (3)$$

Similarly the ratio of the fluorescence quantum yields, F and F_0 in presence and in absence of the quencher Q, is given by

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + \frac{k_3[\text{Q}]}{k_2 + k_4 + k_6} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the straight lines obtained by plotting k_0/k and F_0/F versus quencher concentration [Q], should have identical slopes.

The photobleaching of riboflavin was found to follow first order kinetics with respect to riboflavin concentration. The values of the rate constant (k) were determined from the slope of $-\log \text{O.D.}$ versus time plots (Figs. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1. Plots of log optical density at 445 nm against time during aerobic irradiation of riboflavin: (a) 0, (b) 3.1 mM and (c) 5.1 mM KI present.

The results of kinetic study of aerobic photobleaching of riboflavin in presence of inhibitors, potassium iodide and potassium bromide, at various concentrations are summarised in Fig. 3 as Stern-Volmer plots. The plots are reasonably linear, thus suggesting that only one mechanism is operational in the quenching process. The Stern-Volmer constants of fluorescence and photobleaching quenching obtained from the slopes of the straight lines drawn in Fig. 3 are given in Table 1. In the case

Fig. 2. Plots of log optical density at 445 nm against time during aerobic irradiation of riboflavin; (a) 0, (b) 10.3 mM and (c) 20.6 mM, KBr present.

Fig. 3. Quenching of aerobic photobleaching of riboflavin in aqueous solution by KBr and KI at 37°.

of anaerobic photobleaching of riboflavin the quenching constant for potassium iodide has been calculated to be $173 M^{-1}$ at 23–24° while the fluorescence quenching constant was $50 M^{-1}$. This difference has led Song and Metzlar to assign a triplet mechanism for it¹. In our study, however, the Stern-Volmer constants for fluorescence and photobleaching quenching agree very well with each other both for potassium iodide and potassium bromide in the aerobic condition. If the photobleaching of

riboflavin involves both the singlet and triplet states the photobleaching quenching constant by Br^- should be different by orders of magnitude from that of I^- as the quenching constant of flavin triplet by Br^- is known to be about three hundred times smaller than that of I^- ^{8,10}. This is clearly not the case here.

TABLE I—STERN-VOLMER CONSTANTS OF FLUORESCENCE QUENCHING AND INHIBITION OF AEROBIC PHOTBLEACHING OF RIBOFLAVIN

Quencher	Fluorescence $K_{SV} (M^{-1})$	Photobleaching $K_{SV} (M^{-1})$
KI	60.4	56.9
KBr	29.6	30.3

This experimental study therefore confirms that the first order aerobic photobleaching of riboflavin in aqueous medium involves mainly the singlet state and a general conclusion may be drawn that in presence of any efficient quencher of flavin triplet state the photobleaching of riboflavin would proceed through its singlet state. This is in contrast to the anaerobic photobleaching where usually the inhibition of photobleaching is much greater than the fluorescence quenching at the same concentration of the inhibitor and the photobleaching process is thought to proceed via the triplet state.

Experimental

Riboflavin (Sigma), potassium iodide and potassium bromide (E. Merck) were used as received. Glass-distilled water was used for all the solutions. Riboflavin concentration was monitored by measuring its absorbance at 445 nm on an Elico CL-24 spectrophotometer as the product, lumichrome, did not have any absorption at 445 nm. The light source used for the photobleaching experiments was a Philips 'Comptalux' tungsten spot lamp (24V, 150W) situated 40 cm from the borosilicate glass reaction vessel. To cut off the heat generated by the lamp a 12 cm thick water filter was used. The temperature of the reaction mixture was kept constant at $37 \pm 1^\circ$ by a TWG (E. Germany) contact thermometer controlled circulatory water-bath. Water vapour saturated oxygen gas was bubbled through the reaction mixture during the photobleaching experiment. Fluorescence measurements were performed using air-equilibrated solutions at $37 \pm 1^\circ$ with excitation and emission wavelengths at 445 and 525 nm respectively, on a Perkin-Elmer MPF-44B spectrofluorometer equipped with a Julabo F20-UC temperature controller. Riboflavin concentration used in the fluorescence experiments was $8.6 \times 10^{-6} M$.

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